

An appropriate one-pot synthesis of dihydropyrano[2,3-*c*]pyrazoles and 2-amino-3-cyano-7-hydroxy-4-substituted-4*H*-chromene derivatives using thiourea dioxide as an efficient and reusable organocatalyst

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Abstract : Thiourea dioxide (TUD) was used as a recyclable organocatalyst for the synthesis of 6-amino-4-aryl-5-cyano-3-methyl-1-phenyl-1,4-dihydropyrano[2,3-*c*]pyrazoles and 2-amino-3-cyano-7-hydroxy-4-substituted-4*H*-chromene derivatives via the condensation reaction of 3-methyl-1-phenyl-1*H*-pyrazol-5(4*H*)-one and resorcinol, respectively, with aromatic aldehydes and malononitrile in water. The organocatalyst showed similar efficiency when reused in consecutive reactions.

Keywords : Thiourea dioxide, 3-methyl-1-phenyl-1*H*-pyrazol-5(4*H*)-one, resorcinol, dihydropyrano[2,3-*c*]pyrazole, 4-substituted-4*H*-chromene.

Introduction

Multi-component reactions (MCRs) have emerged as a powerful tool for the construction of novel and complex molecular structures due to their advantages over conventional multi-step synthesis. The major advantages of MCRs include lower costs, shorter reaction times, high atom-economy, energy saving, and the avoidance of time consuming and expensive purification processes. It is established that MCRs are generally much more environmentally friendly, and offer rapid access to large compound libraries with diverse functionalities¹.

4*H*-Pyran play an essential role as biologically active compounds and represent an interesting template for medicinal chemistry. Many of these compounds are known for their potential applications in pharmaceutical field. They exhibit a wide range of biological activities like such as antimicrobial², antiviral³, mutagenicity⁴, sex pheromone⁵, cancer therapy⁶ and central nervous system activity⁷. Some of these compounds are widely employed as cosmetics and pigments and as potential biodegradable agrochemicals⁸. Furthermore, they play a significant role as potential calcium channel antagonists which are structurally similar to biologically active 1,4-dihydropyridines⁹.

Therefore, the synthesis of such compounds has attracted strong interest.

Several protocols for the synthesis of 2-amino-4*H*-chromenes using various catalysts such as potassium phthalimide-*N*-oxyl¹⁰, electrochemically induced reaction in the presence of NaBr as an electrolyte¹¹, ionic liquid¹², ultrasound irradiation¹³, phenylboronic acid¹⁴, nanocrystalline MgO¹⁵ and silica-bonded *N*-propylpiperazine sodium *n*-propionate¹⁶ have been reported previously. These catalysts are either expensive or not suitable for preparation of some compounds. Thus, development of an inexpensive, mild, general and reusable catalyst for MCRs remains an issue of interest.

One of the main challenges in medicinal chemistry is the design and synthesis of biologically active molecules. Dihydropyrano[2,3-*c*]pyrazoles play an essential role as biologically active compounds and represent an interesting template for medicinal chemistry. Many of these compounds are known for their potential applications in pharmaceutical field. They exhibit a wide range of biological activities like insecticidal¹⁷, antimicrobial¹⁸, anticancer^{19,20}, anti-inflammatory²¹, inhibitors of human Chk1 kinase²² and also molluscicidal activity²³. Furthermore,

they play a significant role as crucial synthetic intermediates²⁴.

Pyrazolone ring system represents an important class of compounds not only for their theoretical interest but also for their analgesic, anti-inflammatory, antipyretic and toxicological evaluation²⁵. Aldose reductase is the key enzyme of polypol pathway leading to accumulation of sorbitol. Some novel pyrazolone derivatives were evaluated as inhibitors of aldose reductase *in silico* analysis²⁶. Some novel pyrazolone derivatives attached to a pyrimidine moiety were synthesized by microwave assisted method and evaluated as their anti-inflammatory, analgesic and antipyretic activities²⁷.

During the last few years, synthesis of dihydropyrano[2,3-*c*]pyrazoles has received great interest due to their biological and other significance²⁸⁻³⁶. Recently, 1,4-dihydropyrano[2,3-*c*]pyrazoles are synthesized involving a four-component reaction between hydrazine hydrate, ethyl acetoacetate, benzaldehyde and malononitrile using per-6-amino- β -cyclodextrin under solvent-free condition²⁸, L-proline in water²⁹, amberlyst A21 in ethanol at room temperature³⁰, titanium dioxide nano-sized particles³¹, [DBU][Ac]³² and heterogeneous reusable catalysts³³.

Dihydropyrano[2,3-*c*]pyrazoles are also synthesized from an one-pot three-component process from 3-methyl-1-phenyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one, aromatic aldehydes and malononitrile in aqueous ethanol medium³⁴ and *p*-dodecylbenzenesulfonic acid (DBSA) as the catalyst in aqueous media³⁵. A concise synthesis of 6-amino-3-(trifluoromethyl)-1,4-dihydro-1-phenyl-4-arylpyrano[2,3-*c*]pyrazole-5-carbonitriles by the reaction of aryl aldehydes, malononitrile, and 1-phenyl-3-(trifluoromethyl)-1*H*-pyrazol-5(4*H*)-one was reported in aqueous media without catalyst³⁶. Most of these procedures require refluxing for hours in organic solvents, use of expensive catalysts and tedious work-up. In view of the above-mentioned observations, there is further scope to develop a synthetic methodology using a less expensive and environmentally benign catalyst.

Recently, TUD received considerable attention as an efficient catalyst for the construction of carbon-carbon and carbon hetero atom bonds due to its eco-friendly nature, easy handling, high reactivity and easy work-up

procedures. TUD is reported as a novel organocatalyst in the one-pot synthesis of a library of novel heterocyclic compounds³⁷, hydrolysis of imines³⁸, synthesis of naphthopyran derivatives³⁹ and catalytic oxidation of alcohols⁴⁰.

Organocatalysis is the acceleration of chemical reactions with a substoichiometric amount of an organic compound which does not contain a metal atom. Among the recently developed advancements, the discovery of catalysis by small organic molecules termed as "organocatalysts" has become a break-through, which offers numerous advantages including lower activation energy, high stability, metal free environment and mild reaction conditions³⁷. Moreover, they are usually robust, inexpensive, readily available, and non-toxic.

TUD is easily prepared⁴¹ by the oxidation of thiourea with hydrogen peroxide. It is highly stable and possesses the ability to activate organic substrates through hydrogen bonding. Owing to the presence of two extra oxygen atoms it forms strong hydrogen bonding and can provide higher activation than the corresponding thiourea. In addition, thiourea dioxide is insoluble in common organic solvents and therefore can easily be recovered at the end of the reaction for its reuse³⁷.

The development of eco-friendly methodologies that are environmentally benign and waste-free, as well as being able to produce the desired products in high purity, have received significant levels of attention in recent years because of the increasing tendency of the chemical industry towards greener processes. To reach this goal of greener processes, the use of green reaction media, reagents, and catalysts has been investigated extensively. Water represents a unique solvent in organic synthesis and attracted a great deal of attention as it is inexpensive, safe, environmentally benign and also shows novel reactivity and selectivity for the synthesis of simple organic compounds⁴²⁻⁴⁴.

As a part of our efforts to develop new synthetic methods in heterocyclic chemistry⁴⁵⁻⁴⁷ and also in the application of TUD in the synthesis of pyrano[4,3-*b*]pyrans, 4-aryl-2-naphthalen-2-yl-5*H*-indeno[1,2-*b*]pyridin-5-ones and 3,4-dihydropyrano[3,2-*c*]chromenes in water⁴⁸⁻⁵⁰ herein we report for TUD catalyzed synthesis of a series of 6-amino-4-aryl-5-cyano-3-methyl-1-phenyl-1,4-

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dihydropyrano[2,3-*c*]pyrazoles and 2-amino-3-cyano-7-hydroxy-4-substituted-4*H*-chromene derivatives via the condensation reaction of aromatic aldehydes and malononitrile with 3-methyl-1-phenyl-1*H*-pyrazol-5(4*H*)-one and resorcinol, respectively (Scheme 1).

appropriate time at 70 °C. After completion of the reaction (TLC monitoring), the reaction mixture was poured into 100 mL water, the solid filtered off, and washed with water. The remaining aqueous TUD was reused as such for subsequent runs. The crude products were puri-

Scheme 1. Synthesis of 6-amino-4-aryl-5-cyano-3-methyl-1-phenyl-1,4-dihydropyrano[2,3-*c*]pyrazoles and 2-amino-3-cyano-7-hydroxy-4-substituted-4*H*-chromene derivatives.

Experimental

Apparatus and analysis :

Chemicals were purchased from Merck, Fluka and Aldrich Chemical Companies. All yields refer to isolated products unless otherwise stated. ¹H NMR (500 MHz) and ¹³C NMR (125 MHz) spectra were obtained using Bruker DRX-500 Avance at ambient temperature, using TMS as internal standard. FT-IR spectra were obtained as KBr discs on Shimadzu spectrometer. Mass spectra were determined on a Varion-Saturn 2000 GC/MS instrument. Elemental analysis was measured by means of Perkin-Elmer 2400 CHN elemental analyzer flowchart.

*General procedure for the preparation of 6-amino-4-aryl-5-cyano-3-methyl-1-phenyl-1,4-dihydropyrano[2,3-*c*]pyrazole derivatives :*

To a mixture of aromatic aldehyde (1 mmol), malonitrile (1 mmol) and 3-methyl-1-phenyl-1*H*-pyrazol-5(4*H*)-one (1 mmol) in 5 mL of water, TUD catalyst (10 mol%) was added, and the mixture was refluxed for an

appropriate time at 70 °C. After completion of the reaction (TLC monitoring), the reaction mixture was poured into 100 mL water, the solid filtered off, and washed with water. The remaining aqueous TUD was reused as such for subsequent runs. The crude products were puri-

Spectral data for the synthesized compounds (4a-l) :
*6-Amino-5-cyano-3-methyl-1,4-diphenyl-1,4-dihydropyrano[2,3-*c*]pyrazole (4a) :*

IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3466, 3311, 2196, 1664, 1588, 1255, 1127, 1019, 755; ¹H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 1.93 (3H, s, CH₃), 4.77 (1H, s, CH), 6.80 (2H, s, NH₂), 7.16–7.51 (10H, m, Ar-H) ppm; ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 9.6, 22.4, 60.9, 118.0, 118.6, 119.6, 124.8, 126.1, 126.6, 127.8, 128.4, 129.3, 130.5, 137.9, 150.8, 177.1 ppm; MS (ESI) : *m/z* 329 (M+H)⁺; Anal. Calcd. for C₂₀H₁₆N₄O : C, 73.17; H, 4.88; N, 17.07%. Found : C, 73.10; H, 4.84; N, 17.00%.

*6-Amino-4-(4-chlorophenyl)-5-cyano-3-methyl-1-phenyl-1,4-dihydropyrano[2,3-*c*]pyrazole (4b) :*

IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3478, 3300, 2188, 1662, 1594, 1258,

1122, 1017, 751; ^1H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO- d_6) : δ 1.88 (3H, s, CH₃), 4.72 (1H, s, CH), 6.86 (2H, s, NH₂), 7.06 (2H, d, J 8.4 Hz, Ar-H), 7.22 (2H, d, J 8.4 Hz, Ar-H), 7.40–7.60 (5H, m, Ar-H) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, DMSO- d_6) : δ 9.3, 21.7, 60.1, 118.4, 118.8, 119.3, 124.7, 126.3, 126.8, 127.9, 128.3, 129.6, 130.0, 138.4, 151.0, 176.7 ppm; MS (ESI) : m/z 363.45 (M+H)⁺; Anal. Calcd. for C₂₀H₁₅ClN₄O : C, 66.22; H, 4.14; N, 15.45%. Found : C, 66.08; H, 4.04; N, 15.33%.

6-Amino-4-(4-fluorophenyl)-5-cyano-3-methyl-1-phenyl-1,4-dihydropyran[2,3-c]pyrazole (4c) :

IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3470, 3314, 2194, 1655, 1593, 1262, 1121, 1023, 761; ^1H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO- d_6) : δ 1.82 (3H, s, CH₃), 4.70 (1H, s, CH), 6.92 (2H, s, NH₂), 7.12 (2H, d, J 8.4 Hz, Ar-H), 7.31 (2H, d, J 8.4 Hz, Ar-H), 7.47–7.65 (5H, m, Ar-H) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, DMSO- d_6) : δ 8.8, 22.6, 60.6, 117.4, 118.2, 119.7, 124.5, 125.5, 127.0, 127.7, 128.6, 129.2, 130.7, 137.7, 150.5, 177.4 ppm; MS (ESI) : m/z 347 (M+H)⁺; Anal. Calcd. for C₂₀H₁₅FN₄O : C, 69.36; H, 4.33; N, 16.18%. Found : C, 69.38; H, 4.35; N, 16.19%.

6-Amino-4-(4-bromophenyl)-5-cyano-3-methyl-1-phenyl-1,4-dihydropyran[2,3-c]pyrazole (4d) :

IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3482, 3321, 2199, 1667, 1599, 1260, 1126, 1026, 762; ^1H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO- d_6) : δ 1.96 (3H, s, CH₃), 4.82 (1H, s, CH), 6.90 (2H, s, NH₂), 7.17 (2H, d, J 8.4 Hz, Ar-H), 7.35 (2H, d, J 8.4 Hz, Ar-H), 7.49–7.72 (5H, m, Ar-H) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, DMSO- d_6) : δ 8.6, 21.4, 60.3, 117.7, 118.3, 119.5, 125.3, 125.7, 126.4, 128.4, 128.8, 129.7, 130.6, 138.3, 151.3, 176.8 ppm; MS (ESI) : m/z 407.9 (M+H)⁺; Anal. Calcd. for C₂₀H₁₅BrN₄O : C, 58.98; H, 3.69; N, 13.76%. Found : C, 58.90; H, 3.62; N, 13.71%.

6-Amino-4-(4-methylphenyl)-5-cyano-3-methyl-1-phenyl-1,4-dihydropyran[2,3-c]pyrazole (4e) :

IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3477, 3324, 2202, 1671, 1586, 1270, 1132, 1025, 758; ^1H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO- d_6) : δ 1.90 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.21 (3H, s, CH₃), 4.75 (1H, s, CH), 6.84 (2H, s, NH₂), 7.11 (2H, d, J 8.4 Hz, Ar-H), 7.24 (2H, d, J 8.4 Hz, Ar-H), 7.41–7.59 (5H, m, Ar-H) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, DMSO- d_6) : δ 9.4, 19.6, 22.3, 60.7, 117.9, 118.7, 120.0, 125.6, 125.8, 126.8, 128.2, 128.6, 129.6, 129.9, 137.8, 150.9, 177.0 ppm; MS (ESI) : m/z 343 (M+H)⁺; Anal. Calcd. for C₂₁H₁₈N₄O : C,

73.68; H, 5.26; N, 16.37%. Found : C, 73.58; H, 5.24; N, 16.36%.

6-Amino-4-(4-methoxyphenyl)-5-cyano-3-methyl-1-phenyl-1,4-dihydropyran[2,3-c]pyrazole (4f) :

IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3474, 3316, 2206, 1663, 1597, 1263, 1134, 1018, 750; ^1H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO- d_6) : δ 1.85 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.63 (3H, s, OCH₃), 4.69 (1H, s, CH), 6.89 (2H, s, NH₂), 7.09 (2H, d, J 8.4 Hz, Ar-H), 7.21 (2H, d, J 8.4 Hz, Ar-H), 7.48–7.64 (5H, m, Ar-H) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, DMSO- d_6) : δ 9.5, 21.2, 55.8, 61.0, 118.4, 118.8, 120.3, 125.7, 125.9, 127.2, 128.0, 128.8, 129.1, 129.8, 138.5, 151.4, 176.6 ppm; MS (ESI) : m/z 359 (M+H)⁺; Anal. Calcd. for C₂₁H₁₈N₄O₂ : C, 70.39; H, 5.03; N, 15.64%. Found : C, 70.42; H, 5.06; N, 15.54%.

6-Amino-4-(4-hydroxyphenyl)-5-cyano-3-methyl-1-phenyl-1,4-dihydropyran[2,3-c]pyrazole (4g) :

IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3464, 3308, 2190, 1662, 1594, 1259, 1124, 1022, 764; ^1H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO- d_6) : δ 1.94 (3H, s, CH₃), 4.74 (1H, s, CH), 6.91 (2H, s, NH₂), 7.15 (2H, d, J 8.4 Hz, Ar-H), 7.36 (2H, d, J 8.4 Hz, Ar-H), 7.51–7.63 (5H, m, Ar-H), 9.54 (1H, s, OH) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, DMSO- d_6) : δ 8.9, 22.4, 61.3, 117.5, 118.2, 119.8, 125.0, 126.0, 127.3, 128.5, 128.7, 129.4, 129.7, 137.5, 150.7, 177.5 ppm; MS (ESI) : m/z 345 (M+H)⁺; Anal. Calcd. for C₂₀H₁₆N₄O₂ : C, 69.77; H, 4.65; N, 16.28%. Found : C, 69.66; H, 4.60; N, 16.22%.

6-Amino-4-(4-nitrophenyl)-5-cyano-3-methyl-1-phenyl-1,4-dihydropyran[2,3-c]pyrazole (4h) :

IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3478, 3324, 2193, 1659, 1589, 1261, 1121, 1024, 753; ^1H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO- d_6) : δ 1.97 (3H, s, CH₃), 4.79 (1H, s, CH), 6.93 (2H, s, NH₂), 7.18 (2H, d, J 8.4 Hz, Ar-H), 7.28 (2H, d, J 8.4 Hz, Ar-H), 7.54–7.66 (5H, m, Ar-H) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, DMSO- d_6) : δ 8.8, 22.0, 61.2, 117.3, 118.3, 120.1, 124.9, 126.3, 126.9, 127.8, 128.2, 129.0, 129.9, 138.0, 151.1, 176.9 ppm; MS (ESI) : m/z 374 (M+H)⁺; Anal. Calcd. for C₂₀H₁₅N₅O₃ : C, 64.34; H, 4.02; N, 18.76%. Found : C, 64.24; H, 4.01; N, 18.63%.

6-Amino-4-(3-chlorophenyl)-5-cyano-3-methyl-1-phenyl-1,4-dihydropyran[2,3-c]pyrazole (4i) :

IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3480, 3322, 2200, 1666, 1592, 1271,

1120, 1029, 756; ^1H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO- d_6) : δ 1.89 (3H, s, CH₃), 4.80 (1H, s, CH), 6.95 (2H, s, NH₂), 7.08–7.24 (4H, m, Ar-H), 7.40–7.63 (5H, m, Ar-H) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, DMSO- d_6) : δ 9.7, 22.5, 60.5, 117.9, 118.4, 119.9, 125.8, 126.2, 127.4, 127.9, 128.3, 129.3, 130.3, 137.9, 150.6, 177.8 ppm; MS (ESI) : m/z 363.45 (M+H)⁺; Anal. Calcd. for C₂₀H₁₅ClN₄O : C, 66.22; H, 4.14; N, 15.45%. Found : C, 66.24; H, 4.11; N, 15.42%.

*6-Amino-4-(3-nitrophenyl)-5-cyano-3-methyl-1-phenyl-1,4-dihydropyrano[2,3-*c*]pyrazole (4j)* :

IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3461, 3317, 2205, 1672, 1600, 1266, 1131, 1030, 754; ^1H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO- d_6) : δ 1.96 (3H, s, CH₃), 4.73 (1H, s, CH), 6.86 (2H, s, NH₂), 7.14–7.30 (4H, m, Ar-H), 7.46–7.67 (5H, m, Ar-H) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, DMSO- d_6) : δ 9.9, 21.9, 60.8, 118.3, 118.7, 120.5, 125.5, 126.4, 127.2, 128.1, 128.6, 129.0, 129.5, 137.7, 151.0, 176.1 ppm; MS (ESI) : m/z 374 (M+H)⁺; Anal. Calcd. for C₂₀H₁₅N₅O₃ : C, 64.34; H, 4.02; N, 18.76%. Found : C, 64.36; H, 3.92; N, 18.75%.

*6-Amino-4-(2-chlorophenyl)-5-cyano-3-methyl-1-phenyl-1,4-dihydropyrano[2,3-*c*]pyrazole (4k)* :

IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3484, 3326, 2206, 1663, 1590, 1272, 1122, 1025, 757; ^1H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO- d_6) : δ 1.93 (3H, s, CH₃), 4.84 (1H, s, CH), 6.90 (2H, s, NH₂), 7.02–7.20 (4H, m, Ar-H), 7.47–7.70 (5H, m, Ar-H) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, DMSO- d_6) : δ 9.8, 22.8, 60.8, 117.8, 118.6, 119.6, 125.7, 126.4, 127.4, 127.7, 128.3, 129.3, 130.2, 137.7, 150.3, 178.2 ppm; MS (ESI) : m/z 363.3 (M+H)⁺; Anal. Calcd. for C₂₀H₁₅ClN₄O : C, 66.22; H, 4.14; N, 15.45%. Found : C, 66.15; H, 4.07; N, 15.36%.

*6-Amino-4-(2,4-dichlorophenyl)-5-cyano-3-methyl-1-phenyl-1,4-dihydropyrano[2,3-*c*]pyrazole (4l)* :

IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3477, 3323, 2203, 1665, 1595, 1274, 1117, 1027, 750; ^1H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO- d_6) : δ 1.86 (3H, s, CH₃), 4.77 (1H, s, CH), 6.94 (2H, s, NH₂), 7.11–7.22 (3H, m, Ar-H), 7.37–7.60 (5H, m, Ar-H) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, DMSO- d_6) : δ 9.6, 22.2, 60.2, 117.6, 118.1, 119.6, 125.5, 126.1, 127.2, 127.5, 128.7, 129.7, 130.3, 137.7, 150.7, 177.9 ppm; MS (ESI) : m/z 397.9 (M+H)⁺; Anal. Calcd. for C₂₀H₁₄Cl₂N₄O : C,

60.47; H, 3.53; N, 14.11%. Found : C, 60.40; H, 3.49; N, 14.05%.

General procedure for the synthesis of 2-amino-3-cyano-7-hydroxy-4-substituted-4H-chromene derivatives :

A mixture of resorcinol (1 mmol), aldehyde (1 mmol), malononitrile (1 mmol), water (5 ml) and TUD (10 mol%) was stirred at 70 °C for the appropriate time. After completion of the reaction (TLC monitoring), the reaction mixture was poured into 100 mL water, the solid filtered off, and washed with water. The remaining aqueous TUD was reused as such for subsequent runs. The crude solid product was crystallized from EtOH to afford the pure 2-amino-3-cyano-7-hydroxy-4-substituted-4H-chromene derivatives.

Spectral data for the synthesised compounds (6a-l) :

2-Amino-3-cyano-7-hydroxy-4-phenyl-4H-chromene (6a) :

IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3442 (OH), 3347 (NH₂), 2208 (CN), 1665 (C=C vinyl nitrile), 1597 (C=C aromatic); ^1H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO- d_6) : δ 4.89 (1H, s, CH), 6.27 (2H, s, NH₂), 6.62 (1H, d, *J* 4.0 Hz, Ar-H), 6.79 (1H, dd, *J* 4.0 Hz, 8.0 Hz, Ar-H), 6.92 (1H, d, *J* 8.0 Hz, Ar-H), 7.22–7.35 (5H, m, Ar-H), 9.64 (1H, s, OH) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, DMSO- d_6) : δ 30.1, 58.4, 102.9, 111.3, 117.4, 124.1, 126.1, 127.5, 129.5, 130.7, 143.7, 155.5, 159.8, 176.2 ppm; MS (ESI) : m/z 265 (M+H)⁺; Anal. Calcd. for C₁₆H₁₂N₂O₂ : C, 72.72; H, 4.54; N, 10.60%. Found : C, 72.64; H, 4.50; N, 10.55%.

2-Amino-3-cyano-7-hydroxy-4-(4-chlorophenyl)-4H-chromene (6b) :

IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3444 (OH), 3340 (NH₂), 2214 (CN), 1664 (C=C vinyl nitrile), 1584 (C=C aromatic); ^1H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO- d_6) : δ 4.89 (1H, s, CH), 6.28 (2H, s, NH₂), 6.65 (1H, d, *J* 4.0 Hz, Ar-H), 6.75 (1H, dd, *J* 4.0 Hz, 8.0 Hz, Ar-H), 6.90 (1H, d, *J* 8.0 Hz, Ar-H), 7.25 (2H, d, *J* 7.4 Hz, Ar-H), 7.44 (2H, d, *J* 7.4 Hz, Ar-H), 9.54 (1H, s, OH) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, DMSO- d_6) : δ 29.4, 59.4, 104.4, 110.2, 118.2, 123.2, 125.3, 128.8, 129.4, 131.4, 144.4, 156.4, 158.4, 178.0 ppm; MS (ESI) : m/z 299.45 (M+H)⁺; Anal. Calcd. for C₁₆H₁₁ClN₂O₂ : C, 64.33; H, 3.68; N, 9.38%. Found : C, 64.25; H, 3.63; N, 9.34%.

2-Amino-3-cyano-7-hydroxy-4-(4-fluorophenyl)-4H-chromene (6c) :

IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 3437 (OH), 3341 (NH_2), 2200 (CN), 1672 (C=C vinyl nitrile), 1584 (C=C aromatic); ^1H NMR (500 MHz, $\text{DMSO}-d_6$) : δ 5.11 (1H, s, CH), 6.25 (2H, s, NH_2), 6.68 (1H, d, J 4.0 Hz, Ar-H), 6.78 (1H, dd, J 4.0 Hz, 8.0 Hz, Ar-H), 6.98 (1H, d, J 8.0 Hz, Ar-H), 7.28–7.49 (4H, m, Ar-H), 9.65 (1H, s, OH) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, $\text{DMSO}-d_6$) : δ 30.0, 59.2, 104.3, 110.3, 118.4, 123.6, 125.3, 127.4, 129.7, 130.7, 144.5, 156.5, 158.6, 178.0 ppm; MS (ESI) : m/z 283 (M+H) $^+$; Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{11}\text{FN}_2\text{O}_2$: C, 68.08; H, 3.90; N, 9.93%. Found : C, 68.05; H, 3.82; N, 9.90%.

2-Amino-3-cyano-7-hydroxy-4-(4-bromophenyl)-4H-chromene (6d) :

IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 3443 (OH), 3333 (NH_2), 2199 (CN), 1679 (C=C vinyl nitrile), 1600 (C=C aromatic); ^1H NMR (500 MHz, $\text{DMSO}-d_6$) : δ 4.93 (1H, s, CH), 6.15 (2H, s, NH_2), 6.70 (1H, d, J 4.0 Hz, Ar-H), 6.83 (1H, dd, J 4.0 Hz, 8.0 Hz, Ar-H), 6.93 (1H, d, J 8.0 Hz, Ar-H), 7.30–7.47 (4H, m, Ar-H), 9.56 (1H, s, OH) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, $\text{DMSO}-d_6$) : δ 30.5, 58.5, 103.5, 111.5, 117.5, 124.3, 126.7, 127.7, 129.5, 131.5, 143.8, 155.8, 159.6, 177.9 ppm; MS (ESI) : m/z 343.6 (M+H) $^+$; Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{11}\text{BrN}_2\text{O}_2$: C, 55.99; H, 3.21; N, 8.16%. Found : C, 55.94; H, 3.16; N, 8.09%.

2-Amino-3-cyano-7-hydroxy-4-(4-methylphenyl)-4H-chromene (6e) :

IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 3439 (OH), 3345 (NH_2), 2215 (CN), 1671 (C=C vinyl nitrile), 1583 (C=C aromatic); ^1H NMR (500 MHz, $\text{DMSO}-d_6$) : δ 2.23 (3H, s, CH_3), 4.89 (1H, s, CH), 6.19 (2H, s, NH_2), 6.64 (1H, d, J 4.0 Hz, Ar-H), 6.74 (1H, dd, J 4.0 Hz, 8.0 Hz, Ar-H), 6.84 (1H, d, J 8.0 Hz, Ar-H), 7.27 (2H, d, J 7.4 Hz, Ar-H), 7.52 (2H, d, J 7.4 Hz, Ar-H), 9.66 (1H, s, OH) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, $\text{DMSO}-d_6$) : δ 17.5, 29.3, 58.2, 103.5, 111.4, 117.3, 123.6, 126.7, 127.9, 128.5, 131.5, 143.3, 155.4, 158.6, 178.1 ppm; MS (ESI) : m/z 279 (M+H) $^+$; Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$: C, 73.38; H, 5.03; N, 10.07%. Found : C, 73.31; H, 4.95; N, 9.97%.

2-Amino-3-cyano-7-hydroxy-4-(4-methoxyphenyl)-4H-chromene (6f) :

IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 3433 (OH), 3344 (NH_2), 2216 (CN),

1664 (C=C vinyl nitrile), 1585 (C=C aromatic); ^1H NMR (500 MHz, $\text{DMSO}-d_6$) : δ 3.58 (3H, s, OCH_3), 4.99 (1H, s, CH), 6.24 (2H, s, NH_2), 6.69 (1H, d, J 4.0 Hz, Ar-H), 6.82 (1H, dd, J 4.0 Hz, 8.0 Hz, Ar-H), 6.91 (1H, d, J 8.0 Hz, Ar-H), 7.36 (2H, d, J 7.4 Hz, Ar-H), 7.44 (2H, d, J 7.4 Hz, Ar-H), 9.52 (1H, s, OH) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, $\text{DMSO}-d_6$) : δ 29.0, 54.9, 60.1, 103.9, 110.3, 117.9, 124.3, 125.3, 127.3, 128.3, 131.2, 144.4, 156.3, 159.3, 177.3 ppm; MS (ESI) : m/z 295 (M+H) $^+$; Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3$: C, 69.39; H, 4.76; N, 9.52%. Found : C, 69.31; H, 4.74; N, 9.49%.

2-Amino-3-cyano-7-hydroxy-4-(4-hydroxyphenyl)-4H-chromene (6g) :

IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 3433 (OH), 3437 (OH), 3346 (NH_2), 2200 (CN), 1666 (C=C vinyl nitrile), 1599 (C=C aromatic); ^1H NMR (500 MHz, $\text{DMSO}-d_6$) : δ 4.89 (1H, s, CH), 6.29 (2H, s, NH_2), 6.70 (1H, d, J 4.0 Hz, Ar-H), 6.80 (1H, dd, J 4.0 Hz, 8.0 Hz, Ar-H), 6.89 (1H, d, J 8.0 Hz, Ar-H), 7.27 (2H, d, J 7.4 Hz, Ar-H), 7.62 (2H, d, J 7.4 Hz, Ar-H), 9.60 (1H, s, OH), 9.64 (1H, s, OH) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, $\text{DMSO}-d_6$) : δ 29.5, 59.5, 104.3, 110.4, 118.3, 123.4, 125.6, 128.6, 129.5, 131.5, 143.4, 156.4, 158.6, 178.3 ppm; MS (ESI) : m/z 281 (M+H) $^+$; Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3$: C, 68.57; H, 4.28; N, 10.00%. Found : C, 68.48; H, 4.24; N, 9.92%.

2-Amino-3-cyano-7-hydroxy-4-(4-nitrophenyl)-4H-chromene (6h) :

IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 3441 (OH), 3336 (NH_2), 2195 (CN), 1663 (C=C vinyl nitrile), 1588 (C=C aromatic); ^1H NMR (500 MHz, $\text{DMSO}-d_6$) : δ 5.00 (1H, s, CH), 6.19 (2H, s, NH_2), 6.59 (1H, d, J 4.0 Hz, Ar-H), 6.78 (1H, dd, J 4.0 Hz, 8.0 Hz, Ar-H), 6.95 (1H, d, J 8.0 Hz, Ar-H), 7.29 (2H, d, J 7.4 Hz, Ar-H), 7.55 (2H, d, J 7.4 Hz, Ar-H), 9.58 (1H, s, OH) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, $\text{DMSO}-d_6$) : δ 31.2, 59.0, 104.0, 110.7, 118.1, 124.1, 126.3, 127.5, 129.3, 130.6, 144.5, 155.3, 158.8, 178.1 ppm; MS (ESI) : m/z 310 (M+H) $^+$; Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_3\text{O}_4$: C, 62.13; H, 3.56; N, 13.59%. Found : C, 62.05; H, 3.49; N, 13.51%.

2-Amino-3-cyano-7-hydroxy-4-(3-chlorophenyl)-4H-chromene (6i) :

IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 3445 (OH), 3340 (NH_2), 2218 (CN), 1660 (C=C vinyl nitrile), 1590 (C=C aromatic); ^1H NMR

(500 MHz, DMSO- d_6) : δ 4.85 (1H, s, CH), 6.24 (2H, s, NH₂), 6.64 (1H, d, *J* 4.0 Hz, Ar-H), 6.78 (1H, dd, *J* 4.0 Hz, 8.0 Hz, Ar-H), 6.91 (1H, d, *J* 8.0 Hz, Ar-H), 7.21–7.40 (4H, m, Ar-H), 9.50 (1H, s, OH) ppm; ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, DMSO- d_6) : δ 29.5, 59.5, 104.4, 110.4, 118.3, 123.3, 125.3, 128.6, 129.4, 131.4, 144.4, 156.7, 158.6, 177.7 ppm; MS (ESI) : *m/z* 299.45 (M+H)⁺; Anal. Calcd. for C₁₆H₁₁ClN₂O₂ : C, 64.33; H, 3.68; N, 9.38%. Found : C, 64.27; H, 3.62; N, 9.33%.

2-Amino-3-cyano-7-hydroxy-4-(3-nitrophenyl)-4H-chromene (6j) :

IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3451 (OH), 3343 (NH₂), 2207 (CN), 1657 (C=C vinyl nitrile), 1584 (C=C aromatic); ¹H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO- d_6) : δ 5.08 (1H, s, CH), 6.18 (2H, s, NH₂), 6.58 (1H, d, *J* 4.0 Hz, Ar-H), 6.76 (1H, dd, *J* 4.0 Hz, 8.0, Ar-H), 6.93 (1H, d, *J* 8.0 Hz, Ar-H), 7.27–7.43 (4H, m, Ar-H), 9.54 (1H, s, OH) ppm; ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, DMSO- d_6) : δ 30.3, 58.2, 103.9, 111.1, 117.4, 123.7, 126.3, 127.5, 129.5, 130.8, 144.7, 155.5, 158.4, 177.4 ppm; MS (ESI) : *m/z* 310 (M+H)⁺; Anal. Calcd. for C₁₆H₁₁N₃O₄ : C, 62.13; H, 3.56; N, 13.59%. Found : C, 62.05; H, 3.50; N, 13.58%.

2-Amino-3-cyano-7-hydroxy-4-(2-chlorophenyl)-4H-chromene (6k) :

IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3448 (OH), 3337 (NH₂), 2213 (CN), 1663 (C=C vinyl nitrile), 1593 (C=C aromatic); ¹H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO- d_6) : δ 4.83 (1H, s, CH), 6.23 (2H, s, NH₂), 6.60 (1H, d, *J* 4.0 Hz, Ar-H), 6.79 (1H, dd, *J* 4.0 Hz, 8.0 Hz, Ar-H), 6.97 (1H, d, *J* 8.0 Hz, Ar-H), 7.25–7.41 (4H, m, Ar-H), 9.51 (1H, s, OH) ppm; ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, DMSO- d_6) : δ 29.1, 59.2, 104.3, 110.7, 118.5, 123.5, 125.3, 128.6, 129.6, 131.4, 144.6, 156.7, 158.9, 177.9 ppm; MS (ESI) : *m/z* 299.4 (M+H)⁺; Anal. Calcd. for C₁₆H₁₁ClN₂O₂ : C, 64.33; H, 3.68; N, 9.38%. Found : C, 64.25; H, 3.64; N, 9.34%.

2-Amino-3-cyano-7-hydroxy-4-(2,4-dichlorophenyl)-4H-chromene (6l) :

IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3451 (OH), 3338 (NH₂), 2215 (CN), 1665 (C=C vinyl nitrile), 1597 (C=C aromatic); ¹H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO- d_6) : δ 4.82 (1H, s, CH), 6.24 (2H, s, NH₂), 6.62 (1H, d, *J* 4.0 Hz, Ar-H), 6.77 (1H, dd, *J* 4.0 Hz, 8.0 Hz, Ar-H), 6.98 (1H, d, *J* 8.0 Hz, Ar-H), 7.17–7.36 (3H, m, Ar-H), 9.55 (1H, s, OH) ppm; ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, DMSO- d_6) : δ 29.3, 59.4, 104.4, 110.7, 118.6,

123.7, 125.6, 128.8, 129.8, 131.7, 144.5, 156.4, 158.8, 177.7 ppm; MS (ESI) : *m/z* 333.9 (M+H)⁺; Anal. Calcd. for C₁₆H₁₀Cl₂N₂O₂ : C, 57.67; H, 3.00; N, 8.41%. Found : C, 57.62; H, 2.96; N, 8.37%.

Results and discussion

We have developed an efficient synthesis of a series of 6-amino-4-aryl-5-cyano-3-methyl-1-phenyl-1,4-dihydropyrano[2,3-*c*]pyrazoles and 2-amino-3-cyano-7-hydroxy-4-substituted-4*H*-chromene derivatives in the presence of TUD as an efficient catalyst in water at 70 °C. Herein, we report our results.

*Synthesis of 6-amino-5-cyano-3-methyl-1,4-diphenyl-1,4-dihydropyrano[2,3-*c*]pyrazole :*

In order to find the most appropriate reaction conditions and evaluate the catalytic activity of TUD catalyst, initially a model study to screen the best conditions was carried out on the synthesis of 6-amino-4-aryl-5-cyano-3-methyl-1-phenyl-1,4-dihydropyrano[2,3-*c*]pyrazole **4a** (Table 1). The model reaction involving 1 mmol each of benzaldehyde, malononitrile and 3-methyl-1-phenyl-1*H*-pyrazol-5(4*H*)-one using TUD as catalyst.

Table 1. The reaction of 3-methyl-1-phenyl-1*H*-pyrazol-5(4*H*)-one, benzaldehyde and malononitrile in the presence of catalyst (10 mol%) in different reaction conditions^a

Entry	Catalyst	Solvent	Temp. (°C)	Time (min)	Yield (%) ^b
1	TUD	1,4-Dioxane	Reflux	90	51
2	TUD	CH ₃ CN	Reflux	90	55
3	TUD	THF	Reflux	90	48
4	TUD	CHCl ₃	Reflux	90	36
5	TUD	MeOH	Reflux	60	72
6	TUD	EtOH	Reflux	60	74
7	TUD	Water	70	40	90
8	TUD	Water	rt	120	48
9	TUD	Water	50	90	68
10	TUD	Water	60	60	79
11	TUD	Water	80	40	90
12	PPh ₃	Water	70	90	62
13	NaHCO ₃	Water	70	60	72
14	(NH ₄) ₂ HPO ₄	Water	70	50	81
15	KH ₂ PO ₄	Water	70	90	62

^aReaction conditions : benzaldehyde **1a** (1 mmol), malononitrile **2** (1 mmol) and 3-methyl-1-phenyl-1*H*-pyrazol-5(4*H*)-one **3** (1 mmol).

^bIsolated yields.

To evaluate the effect of solvent, we studied the model reaction in the presence of 10 mol% of TUD as catalyst in refluxing in the presence of various solvents like 1,4-dioxane, CH₃CN, THF, CHCl₃, MeOH, EtOH and water (Table 1, entries 1–7). Aprotic solvents gave moderate yield of the expected product while protic solvents have pleasant to excellent yield. Obviously water was the solvent of choice owing to its higher yield of the desired product, cost effectiveness and environmental acceptability (Table 1, entry 7).

Further investigations were done by using different temperatures including room temperature and 50, 60, 70 and 80 °C (Table 1, entries 7–11). With an increase in temperature of the reaction from room temperature to 70 °C, the reaction time was decreased. The greatest yield in the shortest reaction time was obtained in water at 70 °C (Table 1, entry 7). The use of water as reaction media is not only advantageous from economical view points but also it is beneficial from environmental and green chemistry standpoints.

Among the tested catalyst such as TUD, triphenyl phosphine PPh₃, sodium bicarbonate NaHCO₃, diammonium hydrogen phosphate (NH₄)₂HPO₄ and potassium dihydrogen phosphate KH₂PO₄ (Table 1, entry 7 and entries 12–15), the condensation of 3-methyl-1-phenyl-2-pyrazol-5(4*H*)-one, benzaldehyde and malononitrile was more facile and proceeded to give highest yield using TUD in water at 70 °C (Table 1, entry 7). The reaction was completed within 40 min and the expected product was obtained in 90% yield.

The possibility of recycling the catalyst is one of the key advantages of this procedure, which was demonstrated using the model reaction. As shown in Fig. 1, the recycled catalyst was used for further runs and its activity did not show any significant decrease even after four runs, the yields ranged from 90% to 86%.

In order to study the generality of this procedure, the applicability of TUD catalyst was then examined for the reaction of a series of aromatic aldehydes with 3-methyl-1-phenyl-1*H*-pyrazol-5(4*H*)-one and malononitrile under the optimized reaction conditions. As expected, satisfactory results were observed, and the results are summarized in Table 2. It is shown that in general a wide range of aldehydes could react with 3-methyl-1-phenyl-1*H*-

Fig. 1. Recyclability of the catalyst : TUD catalyst could be re-used four times without any loss of its activity towards the synthesis of 6-amino-4-phenyl-5-cyano-3-methyl-1-phenyl-1,4-dihydropyrazolo[2,3-*c*]pyrazole.

pyrazol-5(4*H*)-one and malononitrile smoothly and give **4a-l** in good to excellent yields (Table 2, entries 1–12). It is also notable that the electronic property of the aromatic ring of aldehydes have some effects on the rate of the condensation process. Generally speaking, shorter reaction time was needed for the substrates bearing electron-withdrawing groups on the aromatic rings. On the other hand, while substrates bearing electron-donating groups can afford the corresponding products with almost equally satisfactory yields.

We propose the possible following mechanism to account for the reaction. One molecule of aromatic aldehyde **1** was firstly condensed with malononitrile **2** to afford α -cyanocinnamonnitrile derivative (**a**). The formation of α -cyanocinnamonnitrile can be regarded as a fast Knoevenagel addition. The intermediate (**b**) can be formed by the active methylene of **3** by reaction with the electrophilic C=C double bond. Further, the intermediate (**b**) undergo tautomerization to the intermediate (**c**). Then the intermediate (**c**) cyclised by the nucleophilic attack of OH group on the cyano (CN) moiety, finally the expected products **4**. In this process, TUD could promote these reactions (Scheme 2).

Synthesis of 2-amino-3-cyano-7-hydroxy-4-substituted-4*H*-chromenes :

The synthesis of 2-amino-3-cyano-7-hydroxy-4-substituted-4*H*-chromene was investigated by an one-pot, three-

Table 2. Synthesis of various 6-amino-4-aryl-5-cyano-3-methyl-1-phenyl-1,4-dihydropyrano[2,3-*c*]pyrazole derivatives from 3-methyl-1-phenyl-1*H*-pyrazol-5(4*H*)-one, aldehydes and malononitrile catalysed by TUD (10 mol%)^a

Entry	Aldehyde	Product	Time (min)	Yield (%) ^b	M.p (°C)	
					Found	Reported
1	Benzaldehyde	4a	40	90	171–173	170–171 [32]
2	4-Chloro benzaldehyde	4b	30	92	173–175	174–176 [32]
3	4-Fluoro benzaldehyde	4c	30	93	170–172	170–171 [16]
4	4-Bromo benzaldehyde	4d	30	93	175–177	176–177 [16]
5	4-Methyl benzaldehyde	4e	50	84	176–178	177–178 [32]
6	4-Methoxy benzaldehyde	4f	50	83	170–172	171–172 [32]
7	4-Hydroxy benzaldehyde	4g	50	84	209–211	210–212 [32]
8	4-Nitro benzaldehyde	4h	30	93	194–196	195–196 [32]
9	3-Chloro benzaldehyde	4i	40	90	158–160	158–160 [32]
10	3-Nitro benzaldehyde	4j	40	88	190–192	190–191 [32]
11	2-Chloro benzaldehyde	4k	50	83	144–146	145–146 [32]
12	2,4-Dichloro benzaldehyde	4l	50	83	183–185	185–186 [32]

^aReaction conditions : 3-methyl-1-phenyl-1*H*-pyrazol-5(4*H*)-one (1 mmol), aldehyde (1 mmol), malononitrile (1 mmol) in the presence of TUD (10 mol%) at 70 °C.

^bIsolated yield.

Scheme 2. Plausible mechanism of formation of various 6-amino-4-aryl-5-cyano-3-methyl-1-phenyl-1,4-dihydropyrano[2,3-*c*]pyrazoles and 2-amino-3-cyano-7-hydroxy-4-phenyl-4*H*-chromene derivatives catalysed by TUD (10 mol%).

Table 3. Synthesis of various 2-amino-3-cyano-7-hydroxy-4-phenyl-4*H*-chromene derivatives from resorcinol, aldehydes and malononitrile catalysed by TUD (10 mol%)^a

Entry	Aldehyde	Product	Time (min)	Yield (%) ^b	M.p (°C)	
					Found	Reported
1	Benzaldehyde	6a	30	93	234–236	234–237 [11]
2	4-Chloro benzaldehyde	6b	30	92	160–162	161–162 [11]
3	4-Fluoro benzaldehyde	6c	30	94	188–190	187–189 [11]
4	4-Bromo benzaldehyde	6d	30	92	223–225	224–226 [11]
5	4-Methyl benzaldehyde	6e	45	84	184–186	183–186 [11]
6	4-Methoxy benzaldehyde	6f	45	86	110–111	110–112 [11]
7	4-Hydroxy benzaldehyde	6g	45	85	221–223	220–222 [14]
8	4-Nitro benzaldehyde	6h	30	91	233–235	234–236 [14]
9	3-Chloro benzaldehyde	6i	40	87	106–108	106–109 [13]
10	3-Nitro benzaldehyde	6j	40	88	197–198	–
11	2-Chloro benzaldehyde	6k	45	86	187–189	188–190 [10]
12	2,4-Dichloro benzaldehyde	6l	45	88	255–257	256–258 [13]

^aReaction conditions : aldehyde (1 mmol), malononitrile (1 mmol), resorcinol (1 mmol) in the presence of TUD (10 mol%) at 70 °C.

^bIsolated yield.

component condensation reaction between resorcinol, aromatic aldehyde, and malononitrile in the presence of TUD in water at 70 °C. As shown in Table 3, aromatic aldehydes substituted with electron-donating and electron-withdrawing groups reacted under optimized conditions to give the corresponding products in good yields (**6a-l**). The influence of electron-withdrawing and electron-donating substituents on the aromatic ring of aldehydes upon the reaction yields was investigated. The results showed that the reaction times slightly decreased but the yields increased in the presence of electron-withdrawing substituents. With electron releasing groups the reaction times slightly increased and the yields decreased.

A plausible mechanism for the reaction in the presence of TUD is shown in Scheme 2. The α -cyanocinnamionitrile (**a**) formed initially by Knoevenagel condensation in the presence of TUD undergoes subsequent reactions with resorcinol in the presence of TUD to give the desired product.

Conclusions

In conclusion, a procedure for the preparation of 6-amino-4-aryl-5-cyano-3-methyl-1-phenyl-1,4-dihydro-pyran[2,3-*c*]pyrazoles and 2-amino-3-cyano-7-hydroxy-4-substituted-4*H*-chromenes catalyzed by TUD in water at 70 °C have been developed. The mild reaction conditions, simplicity of the procedure, and the ability to reuse

the catalyst are particular advantages of this method. This report has proposed and demonstrated a new useful and attractive process for the synthesis of these compounds.

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